

PHILOSOPHY

LINGUISTIC VICISSITUDES OF OUR TIME

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Abstract

The modern era manifests itself with various characteristics: post-industrial, information, knowledge society, risk, technological, post-colonial, etc., which emphasises its complexity and dynamism and, at the same time, uneven development. The complexity of the era is associated in modern conditions with such processes as globalisation and technologisation, which affect all spheres of social life and the life of an individual, and cause different consequences in the context of the historical characteristics of a country or state. There have also been shifts in intercultural relations. Language plays a significant role in these processes. Thanks to language in the modern world, humanity is developing in close interaction between different peoples, countries and cultures.

Keywords: globalization, monolingual, multilingual, technologisation, Globish, linguistic imperialism vicissitudes.

The modern world is a world of multicoloured communications both at the level of states, countries, communities and individuals. Language reflects not only the mentality but also the peculiarities of human life. According to M. Heidegger, "language is the home of human existence". As the home of human existence, language is a speech action and a speech practice. It is these circumstances that allow us to consider it as a linguistic reality and as a "changing organ of thought" (A. Potebnya). The modern linguistic reality presents itself in various socio-cultural spaces, acting as a "space of coexistence of people". In this sense, Lyotard's idea "everything is language" is appropriate.

Globalisation has raised among scholars of various humanitarian fields the question of the monological and polylogical existence of language in the modern world in the context of technological culture and the technologisation of social and personal life.

In the space of technological society, the discourse on the existence of "live" and "artificial" language, monolingual or multilingual space has become more intense than ever. Scholars are asking the question: are all languages equal, how do language, culture and national identity relate? [3] It is advisable to start with a factual statement of the existing linguistic picture. Encyclopedic and statistical reference books claim that there are 7000 "living" languages today. On average, one language is lost in the world every two weeks, forty languages become the language of 2/3 of the world's population. The most widely spoken languages in the world are Chinese, Hindi, English, Spanish, Arabic, Russian, and Portuguese. This raises the question of national and state languages. According to E. Hobsbawm, this question arises because in the states in which we live, political decisions regarding the conditions of public use of languages (for example, in schools) make a lot of sense. This, in his opinion, is due to the fact that states today are usually identified with the nation. This confusion is dangerous [10, P.49]. Unfortunately, the scientist's prognostic conclusion is not always taken into account in real language policy. This is evidenced by the situa-

tion around the language clause in the "Law on Education", which was adopted by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine in 2017. Discussions about the absolute requirement to teach in Ukrainian at school, despite the fact that there are more than 100 national minorities in Ukraine, have led to a deterioration in international relations with Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, and Russia. The situation has become so alarming that the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine was forced to submit a draft resolution to the Verkhovna Rada to postpone the implementation of this law until 2020. Ukraine is a multilingual state and it is unacceptable not to take into account the emergence of new aspects in the dialogue of states, cultures, multicultural dialogue, the creation of multicultural communities, and the growing need for specialists in various fields who speak foreign languages. Artificial languages, instrumental languages, as defined by M. Foucault, are emerging on the basis of a technologically developed process.

The palette of languages that exists in the world and its analysis in modern realities allowed E. Hobsbawm to make several important observations: 1) today there are not equivalent, but complementary languages, regardless of the presence or absence of their official status; 2) there is a spread of various kinds of lingua franca in different countries and regions; 3) English is spreading as a global means of communication, which is becoming dominant, becoming the ruling "jargon"; 4) political languages emerge, i.e. languages nationally created as symbols of nationalist or regionalist and separatist ideas, which can become "living" languages or fail; 5) all languages have elements of political self-assertion, since in the era of national or regional separatism there are natural tendencies to supplement political independence with linguistic separatism. Language manipulations are based on politics, not culture 6) if language is not clearly separated from the state, it will remain a constant, artificial source of strife. The scientist outlined the new linguistic situation that is the reality of today, the challenges that have arisen as a result of its existence [10, P. 57-58].

In the scientific literature on philosophy of language and linguistics, the analysis of Globish language is insufficiently presented. This topic is being outlined, but there are almost no studies in the Ukrainian scientific discourse. Is such research relevant? We believe that yes, especially in the context of the monolingualism/multilingualism dichotomy, the transfer of one language practice to another language practice of a different social background.

What is the Globish language? According to the reference literature, Globish is a version of English that was proposed and presented by J.-P. Nérières on the basis of English grammar and vocabulary in the amount of 1500 words. J.-P. Nérières qualified the language he presented as a natural language, devoted textbooks to it, and in 2009 he and D. Hohn published "Globish the World Over", the first book written in Globish, which was later translated into 12 languages. Globalisation is becoming a circumstance that calls for interaction between peoples and countries, and the elimination of isolation between them. Communication is one of the means of interconnection in this process. Experts point out that new formats of communication are emerging. The process of global rapprochement and interaction is difficult to imagine without the availability of communication tools that will facilitate such interaction, in particular, without the lingua franca - the language of the intermediary, which will serve as a means of communication and mutual understanding between the subjects of globalisation relations [11, P.204]. The emergence of such a new phenomenon becomes relevant and controversial when considering the linguistic opposition of monolingualism/multilingualism.

Intensive ties between states have acquired the characteristics of a technologically developed process of creating and implementing values, signalling systems that reflect them and socio-cultural practices that are managed through systems of economic expediency and market regulation. These factors give rise to the need not only for national languages, dialects, official and political languages, but also for lingua franca in different countries and regions, and for English as a global medium of communication. The existence of English as the dominant language is perceived rather ambiguously, as evidenced by the emergence of such doctrines as "linguistic imperialism", "linguistic globalisation", "sociolinguistics", "linguistic anti-globalism" [1].

The discourses of "language-nation-state", "language-natural-artificial", "language-culture-mentality" are becoming quite multivariate in our time. They have various variations, one of which is the dichotomy of monolingualism/multilingualism. This dichotomy is exacerbated at different levels of the nation, the state, society, and the individual.

In this context, we consider it appropriate to dwell on the emergence of new linguistic concepts that have become widespread in the modern world, namely the concepts of "linguistic imperialism" and Globish language.

Why is this happening? In the works of foreign researchers on this issue (and there are a rather small number of them in our Ukrainian research field), it is noted that this situation is connected, firstly, with the

dominance of the two empires of Britain and America. Secondly, the language of the Internet is English. Studies show that 80% of information is stored on the World Wide Web in English, and its volume doubles every 18 months [1]. According to A. Khomenko, "the position of English as a lingua franca will remain unshakable for a long time" [9]. However, the researcher, in asserting this position, raises questions that cannot be answered unequivocally. Are there any guarantees of the steadfastness of English as the most popular language in the international arena? Will this reality change in the world if the United States loses its leading position?

The English language is spreading around the world, modifying into various dialects, pidgins, which, according to researchers, are called englishes or glocal English. According to N. Pelegesha, this is how spanglish, greekish, singlish, and tanglish emerged in the modern world. The European Union speaks its own dialect, European English. Its peculiarity is that this language has a limited vocabulary, which is simple and useful to use. Today, more than 51% of people in the EU speak European English. In Ukraine, according to the Institute of Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences, only 1.3% of the population speaks it.

English is becoming a global language or standard world English, and as such it is no longer associated with native speakers, but exists separately, independently, no longer as American or British. It is the second language for EU citizens with a population of almost 500 million. It is spoken by three times as many people as non-native speakers. Experts say that the English-speaking world is almost 1.5 billion people. All of these circumstances explain the establishment of the English language in the world, its features and functioning as a lingua franca [2].

In this context, in the linguistic reality of the globalised world, the language of Globish has emerged as a language of universal communication to meet the language needs of people. This language is defined as a foreign dominant language in the present, as "global English", as a linguistic hybrid. The author, the creator of Globish, J.-P. Nérieur, in response to a question from a "Radio Liberty" correspondent, identified the features of this language: 1) it is different from the English spoken in the US and Britain, it is a completely different English spoken in other countries: Japan, Ukraine, Spain, Korea, all over the globe; 2) Globish is for the purpose of simplifying communication, not a separate language, it prevents cultural references; 3) Globish consists of 1500 words, it uses short sentences, and a sentence should have no more than 20 words; 4) Globish is a form of English, English-lite, dietary English, it is simplified, it has fewer words, simplified grammar. As noted in scientific publications, in the wake of globalisation and technological development, English has conquered the world in a way that no other language in human history has been able to do. This process was facilitated by postmodernism, which radically changed the world linguistic order of the modern era, and global English is a political and cultural reality of the twenty-first century [6].

It is worth noting that in the Ukrainian public space, a discussion has been launched about the need

for popular humanities to speak a simple and understandable language to society without overloading it with specific terminology, explaining in full what a particular term, category or concept means. Such an attempt has already been made in the West, and it is about non-fiction.

Simplification of language and speech practices in modern society is associated with the development of technical means of communication. However, this fact should not significantly affect the culture of language, reduce the level of social requirements for it, as it affects the state of all social practices: education, science, politics, morality, art, which function through language.

The global language in its various forms is debatable in the context of the concept of "linguistic imperialism" or "linguistic imperialism". This term was used after the publication of Robert Phillipson's 1992 work "Linguistic Imperialism". In the national scientific field of philosophy of language, sociolinguistics and linguistics, there are almost no works analysing "linguistic imperialism". Although, from our point of view, this phenomenon is present both in the past and in the present: in the past, it was Russification, the dominance of Russian as the state language in all the Soviet republics, and in the present, the introduction of English as the language of the globe. Referring to Wikipedia, let's define "linguistic imperialism" in several aspects: 1) "linguistic imperialism" is a component of "cultural imperialism"; 2) dominance and maintenance of cultural inequality between English and other languages; 3) marginalisation of local languages and their displacement from use; 4) a threat to linguistic and cultural diversity; 5) a means of cultural hegemony through language.

Monolingualism instead of multilingualism, the hegemony of the English language in modern society, and the emergence of the Globish language are manifestations of "linguistic imperialism"; moreover, these trends indicate rather complex linguistic vicissitudes in today's diverse ethnic society.

Indeed, whether we like it or not, today English, its embodiment, is beginning to play the same role around the world as Latin did in the Middle Ages. According to researchers, it is becoming the "new Latin", the alphabet of education. English is spoken by computers, and this, according to A. Carmine, gives it priority over all other language practices in the foreseeable future. He points out that a lot of English texts are created by those for whom English is not their native language. As an international language, it presents itself in the form of a so-called "mac-language", "MC language" - simplified, reduced beyond hidden connotations and grammatical subtleties. In this form, it cannot become a full-fledged language of world culture, capable of changing and replacing national languages [5, P.57].

In Ukraine, 76% of the population has it, and we rank 10th in the world by this indicator. At the same time, the quality of education remains extremely low. Corruption is rampant in universities, curricula are outdated, and the professionalism of teachers themselves is a source of many complaints.

The 76% figure looks quite different when compared to the proportion of Ukrainians who know English and can communicate fluently. According to an online survey by TNS, only 18% of our citizens speak English at an above-average level. For comparison, in Denmark, Sweden, and the Netherlands, about 70% of the population is fluent in English. According to the annual English Proficiency Index, Ukraine ranks 41st out of 72 countries, and the level of proficiency is defined as low [10, P. 6-12]. These facts are presented on the pages of the Ukrainian Week, No. 40, 2017. Thus, not only specialists and scholars are concerned, but public opinion is already loudly declaring and ringing the bells about the crisis in education. In order to break the vicious circle and move towards a truly educated nation, we need to radically change the emphasis in education. Not to cram tonnes of information into the brains, but to teach how to use it in practice [10, P.12]. We cannot but agree with this conclusion of D. Kazansky.

The results of the English language proficiency test in the past years' admissions campaigns suggest that English as an academic discipline, as a subject, is not perceived by educational subjects (pupils, students) as a requirement of the times, as a component of competence in the field of future professional activity. Unfortunately, to this day, language learning in educational institutions is still treated as a "pass and be done" affair. There is no motivation to learn foreign languages. What motivation could there be if, for example, 86% of the base workers registered in Kharkiv region are people with higher education? These are parents, sisters, and friends of modern schoolchildren and students. A completely new social phenomenon is emerging - learning foreign languages is becoming a commodity: a commodity as a tutoring service, a commodity for bribes for knowledge, a commodity for companies offering language training.

Both schools and universities are public institutions for acquiring educational knowledge. In contrast, other forms of language learning are already becoming widespread, but they are mostly commercial. Language proficiency is becoming a commodity.

Yuriy Makarov's words sound unfortunate but true: "The general level of higher and especially secondary education in the country remains literally cave-like. Our school remains a Prussian gymnasium from the time of Bismarck, which the Russian Empire borrowed at a moment of rare sobriety. Since then, this model has undergone several rebrandings, organically rejecting any innovations and keeping its authoritarian, inertial core intact. It is not capable of instilling any intellectual thirst, let alone a modern critical outlook (however, this does not mean that it should be destroyed, it is a long game)" [10, C. 21].

Every conscious Ukrainian today, in today's reality, is concerned with the question: why, after studying for several years at school and university, are they unable to speak fluently not only foreign languages but also their native language? Why is it that Ukraine is ahead of Germany, Japan, and South Korea in terms of education spending, but we have no breakthrough? Worldview values versus beer and popcorn - this is how Ukraine's civilisational choice is seen today. There is

no evidence to the contrary in the East. Are bureaucratic specialists in education and pedagogy able to not only hear this message, but also change it? It is bitter and sad what is happening in contemporary humanities in Ukraine: "we," as Y. Makarov notes, "are not only not lagging behind - we are not lagging behind anyone at all, we are not visible on the world scientific map of philosophy, linguistics, anthropology of art history" [10, P. 21].

The modern world presents itself as a multilingual space. In the technological world, with the help of the Internet, human communication creates an increasing number of linguistic worlds and uses the entire arsenal of language production in them, both positively and negatively. In this context, the opinion of L. Kapets is correct, as she notes the following: "Excessive openness of communication channels (Internet, mass media, mobile communication) causes human insecurity, provoking dehumanisation of society, having a negative impact on the consciousness and national identity of society as a whole (including direct participants in the educational process). In modern society, the positive potential of multilingualism can be used as one of the possible means of neutralising the negative effects of globalism and the ultra-openness of the socio-cultural space" [4, P. 281]. The author raised a rather important issue - the ambivalence of language and its consequences.

The scientific literature states that the number of languages spoken by humanity will be decreasing. Linguists believe that by the beginning of the twenty-first century, up to 9/10 of the several thousand languages that exist today will disappear from use, although it is emphasised that English will be preserved. Experts ask the question: is there a need and sense in multilingualism or monolingualism for the sake of the prospects of further development of world culture? The vicissitudes of language are dynamic and diverse, and they require a polydigmatic consideration that does not absolutise their consideration in either/or coordinates. There should be a respectful attitude in the coordinates of both/and, which reproduces the multilingual space as a totality, interaction, complementarity, interactivity, and

multilingualism. Language is a social capital, without which the development of modern society and human beings is impossible. For a person of today, G. Skovoroda and Y. Shevelev, who made an invaluable contribution to the development of the Ukrainian language as a manifestation of the culture of the Ukrainian nation, should serve as an example, rather than the characters of Irena Karpa, for whom the ability to learn and think do not constitute the value of being/life. Today, language as a socio-cultural phenomenon is being determined and transform.

The transformation of the status of English in Ukraine is a necessity and a strategic step towards country's full membership in the EU, as knowledge of English is a key competence in the context of globalisation.

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